

Naming of the Koh-i-Noor and the Origin of Mughal-Cut Diamonds

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For centuries, the Koh-i-Noor, or Mountain of Light, has been a diamond of exceptional renown in the East as well as in the West. Several legends circulate regarding this stone, and among these are tales of its origin and the way it received its name. This article attempts to verify the authenticity of these accounts and shows that the true origin of the diamond's name is connected to its appearance achieved through the faceting style known today as the Mughal cut. Although the provenance of this cut has thus far not been determined, this article proposes that it possibly originated in the 16th century in Goa, India, through the Gujaratis and under the influence of European diamond cutters. Various lines of evidence suggest that the Koh-i-Noor may have been worked in the 16th century by an Indian specialist in the Vijayanagara Empire.

The Journal of Gemmology, 35(8), 2017, pp. 738–750, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15506/JoG.2017.35.8.738>
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Introduction

One of the world's most famous diamonds is the Koh-i-Noor, or *Mountain of Light* as it translates from Persian, the language of the Mughal court. The diamond originated in the treasury of the Great Mughals, and is currently mounted in the crown of the Queen Mother (wife of George VI and mother of Elizabeth II), which is kept in the Tower of London. It has the form of an oval brilliant and weighs 102.8125 English carats or 105.59 metric carats (Tennant, 1854b). The original Mughal-cut stone (cf. Figure 1) weighed 589.82 troy grains, corresponding to 186.0625 English carats, which is equivalent to about 191.09 metric carats (Tennant, 1854b; Story-Maskelyne, 1860) or 191.03 ct (Carriere and Sucher, 2008). It reached the United Kingdom in 1850 from India, where it was confiscated by the British from the last maharaja of the Sikh Empire, Dulip Singh (r. 1843–1849). For more background on this important stone, see Mīrzā 'Aṭā Muḥammad (1952–1953 (AH 1331), Bukhārī (1958

[AH 1337]), Howarth (1980), Gill (1982), Amini (1994), 'Ayn al-Saltanah, (1995–2000), Shirazi and Muḥaddiṣ (2000) and Dalrymple and Anand (2016).

Several legends have circulated on the topic of the Koh-i-Noor, including a commonly cited story of how its name originated. According to contemporary gem writers, its name was assigned in Delhi, at the court of the Mughal emperor Muhammad Shah (r. 1719–1748); the person instrumental in giving the stone its name was the king of Iran, Nadir Shah (r. 1736–1747). The Shah of Persia invaded the Mughal capital in March 1739, after the battle at Karnal in which he overpowered the Indian armies. Although Nadir Shah did not deprive Muhammad Shah of the throne, he also did not refrain from confiscating his legendary treasures (Astarabadi and Rashad, 1994). The conqueror's interest was piqued by the huge diamond in the Mughal emperor's possession. The existence of this gem was told to the invader, it is said, by a woman from the Mughal's harem.

She was said to have revealed that her lord had a habit of carrying the stone in the folds of his turban. In order to take the gem while maintaining the appearance of respect for the conquered royal, Nadir Shah developed a ploy in which he proposed to the Indian emperor an exchange of headdresses, which symbolized friendship. The Mughal could do nothing else but hand over his turban, which contained the gem inside. Upon seeing its glow, Nadir Shah exclaimed “Koh-i-Noor”, thus giving the diamond its name (Street-er, 1882; Amini, 1994; Balfour, 2009).

Although the authenticity of this legend has recently been questioned (Dalrymple and Anand, 2016), contemporary writers have not researched, to the present author’s knowledge, the true origin of the name *Koh-i-Noor*.¹ In the present author’s view, the name refers to the appearance of the diamond’s faceting style, known today as the Mughal cut. Based on the analysis of gemmological material, researchers do not state unequivocally if this cut, widespread in Indian territory, was indigenous or created under Western influence. This article analyses primary literature sources from the 15th to the 17th centuries, as well as iconographic material, to investigate this matter and the validity of the stories about the naming of the Koh-i-Noor.

Investigating the Tale of Koh-i-Noor’s Name

The meeting of Nadir Shah and the defeated Mughal emperor did in fact take place, and the conqueror of Delhi did receive diamonds at that time (Malecka, in preparation). Analysis of sources from the epoch, however, indicates that the Koh-i-Noor could not have been one of them (Anonymous, 1866–1867 [AH 1283]). According to Nadir Shah’s chronicler, a diamond called the Koh-i-Noor was indeed among jewels confiscated by his lord from the Mughal emperor, but it had been placed in the famous Peacock Throne of the Mughals—and not in the folds of the monarch’s turban—as a decoration on the head of the eponymous bird adorning it. The historiographer of the king of Iran is a credible source, in the present author’s view, because he saw the Peacock Throne in the Afghan city of Herat, to which it was transported from Delhi upon the order of the conqueror (Marvī et al., 1991; see also Tihrani and Sha’bāni, 1990 [AH 1369]). Since it follows that the name *Koh-i-Noor*

Figure 1: This glass replica of the Koh-i-Noor diamond, as it appeared when it reached Great Britain in 1850, resides at the Corning Museum of Glass in Corning, New York, USA. It was made in 1851 by Falcon Glassworks of Apsley Pellatt & Co., London. More information is available at www.cmog.org/artwork/replica-koh-i-noor-diamond; courtesy of the Corning Museum of Glass.

already was used in the Mughal court in reference to this diamond, the name could not have been assigned by Nadir Shah.

How, then, did the story arise that Nadir Shah conferred the name on this diamond? None of the Persian sources from the time of Nadir Shah, to the present author’s knowledge, cite this story. It appeared for the first time in the tale of the Koh-i-Noor written in 1850 by Theophilus Metcalfe, a functionary of the East India Company who, upon the order of the Governor-General of India, gathered stories circulating in Delhi on

¹ An author from the Indian subcontinent who was active at the end of the 19th century stated, without justifying his opinion, that the episode wherein the Koh-i-Noor was gained by exchange of turbans was untrue (Latif, 1956).

the topic of this stone (Singh and Singh, 1985; Kinsey, 2012; Dalrymple and Anand, 2016).² Metcalfe's report was not published. In printed form, one of the earliest English-language publications of this story was the catalogue of the Great Exhibition of 1851, at which the Mountain of Light was presented to the public (Ellis, 1851).

It also should be mentioned that, with regard to the Koh-i-Noor, the tale of the exchange of turbans did appear in Persian-language sources, but for a different owner of the stone: Ranjit Singh, the father of Dulip Singh. In 1813, this monarch forced the ex-king of Afghanistan, Shah Shuja Durrani, who at that time possessed the stone, to surrender it in order to close an agreement of friendship with him. To seal this pact, as Durrani himself affirmed in his memoirs, Ranjit Singh exchanged headdresses with him, and after this ceremony came the presentation of the stone (Shuja Shah, 1914/1915 [AH 1333]).

It is probable that this event had an impact on the development of the story about the acquisition of the Koh-i-Noor by Nadir Shah. It should be emphasized, however, that tales of the exchange of headdresses as a means to swindle gems had been circulating in India in earlier times. For example, a 19th-century researcher mentioned, on the basis of unpublished family annals of the rulers of the Chota Nagpur in India, that a similar event had taken place in 1772 (Dalton, 1872). According to this account, a British officer wished to acquire diamonds that the rajah of Chota Nagpur carried in his turban, and proposed to the ruler the exchange of headdresses as a gesture of eternal friendship, claiming this custom also was practised in Great Britain.

It should be underlined that the authors who saw the Koh-i-Noor in the court of Ranjit Singh do not refer to exchanging headdresses while mentioning its acquisition by Nadir Shah (Osborne, 1840; Hügel, 1848). It seems that this story gained popularity in the 1840s, both as a result of the wheedling tales that circulated in India during the Mughal epoch, as well as the actual turban exchange that accompanied the earlier transfer of the Koh-i-Noor in 1813.

Connection Between the Koh-i-Noor's Name and Its Appearance

Researchers have been unable to explain how the Koh-i-Noor was originally included among the several hundred large diamonds in the Mughal treasury that were confiscated by Na-

dir Shah. In the present author's view, the stone was already in the possession of these rulers in the 1500s. It is known that a diamond weighing about 190 ct had been the property of Emperor Akbar (r. 1556–1605; AMIDRF, 1740; Malecka, in preparation). Even though Akbar's stone was the only diamond of such weight in the possession of the Mughals mentioned in 16th-century sources, we cannot simply assume it to be identical with the Koh-i-Noor on the basis of its approximate weight.³ A mention of its shape allows a greater probability of identifying it as the Koh-i-Noor. Akbar's diamond was described by an author from the epoch (Malecka, in preparation) as having the form of a pyramid, which does correspond to the shape of the original Koh-i-Noor (Figures 1 and 2, left). Considering such factors as weight, shape and Mughal provenance, the identification of Akbar's stone as the Koh-i-Noor seems justified.

It is probable that Akbar had obtained the stone from the Vijayanagara Empire (1336–1646) in the southern part of the Indian subcontinent, which abounded in diamond mines.⁴ Sources from the turn of the 16th/17th centuries mention a diamond of fabulous value purchased by the Great Mughal from the ruler of Vijayanagara.⁵ In the present author's opinion, it is probable that the Koh-i-Noor remained in the Mughal treasury continuously from around 1600 to 1739, when it was looted by Nadir Shah. This is supported by the fact that Jahangir (r. 1605–1627), the son of

² Mention of the mythical history of the Koh-i-Noor did, however, appear in the British press in earlier years (Anonymous, 1849).

³ Sixteenth-century sources also mention the so-called Babur's diamond. Some contemporary authors infer it to be identical with the Koh-i-Noor on the basis of its alleged weight of about 186 carats (Beveridge, 1899). In reality, Babur's diamond weighed significantly less than the Koh-i-Noor, and most probably it also was a rough stone (Malecka, in preparation).

⁴ After the battle at Talikota in 1565 between the Vijayanagara Empire and a coalition of Muslim kingdoms of the Deccan, the mines gradually passed under the rule of Golconda, contributing to building the fame of the sultanate as the global diamond capital at the time. The mines were famous for producing exceptionally large stones, as attested by the following comparison: In the Mughal Empire, rough stones weighing as little as 2.5 ct automatically passed to ownership by the emperor, while in Vijayanagara the weight of diamonds subject to the monopoly of the king was set above 20–30 ct (Orta, 1891; Lopes, 1897; Foster, 1921; Vassallo e Silva, 1989). See also footnote 12.

Figure 2: These line drawings prepared by Al Gilbertson compare the appearance of the Koh-i-Noor before (left) and after re-cutting (right) in 1852. The cuts are shown from the top and side views.

Akbar, was in possession of a diamond of similar weight (Malecka, in preparation).

The Koh-i-Noor was presumably wheel cut into a 169-facet stone measuring $40.85 \times 32.57 \times 16.18$ mm (Carriere and Sucher, 2008).⁶ It had a high-domed crown and flat base, with predominantly triangular and pentagonal facets (resembling rectangles with triangular pinnacles) covering its surface (Figure 2, left). It seems most probable that the Koh-i-Noor received its name because of the shape it was given during this ‘rough fashioning’, which was reminiscent of a mountain (Younghusband and Davenport, 1919).⁷ It was common in the East to give names to gems that referred to their appearance, and particularly large stones were sometimes described as ‘mountains’. Other important gems with names alluding to mountains include the Koh-i-Toor (or Sinai Mountain diamond), as well as al-Jabal (or Mountain), a huge red stone that was the property of the Abbasid caliphs (Ibn al-Zubayr et al., 1959; Ibn al-Athir, 1995; Malecka, in preparation). According to mistaken suppositions by some researchers, the full name of this last stone was Jabal al-Noor, or Mountain of Light, arising supposedly from translation of the Persian words *Koh-i-Noor* (Herzfeld, 1948). Islamic sources also mention other precious stones having the name of ‘Mountain’ (Farmān-Farmāyān, 1962; Malecka, in preparation).

The second part of the Koh-i-Noor’s name has a connection to radiance. Names of large stones held by the Mughals often contained allusions to brilliance by including such words as *sun*, *moon* or *light* (Linschoten et al., 1885; Manucci and Irvine, 1907). Radiance was of key importance to

the Islamic monarchy, because it was believed to embody the invisible perfection of God. Radiance attested to the connection between God and the ruler, who governed in His name on Earth (Bedik,

⁵ A discussion of sources referring to this diamond is presented in Malecka (in preparation). Even though rulers in the East unwillingly parted with exceptional diamonds, a stone of 190 ct would certainly not have been deemed unique by Vijayanagara rulers, as their diamond treasury contained specimens weighing several hundreds of carats. In the 15th century, before the Mughal emperor Shah Jahan ordered construction of the Peacock Throne, similar fame was attributed in the East to the diamond throne of Vijayanagara, which was described as priceless (Sousa, 1666; Goes, 1749; Malecka, in preparation). It is probable that the reason the Koh-i-Noor (assuming it was identical to the diamond purchased from the Vijayanagara ruler) was sold to the Mughal was that it contained some blemishes (see below). It is known that Vijayanagara royals would sell large imperfect diamonds that they considered inauspicious (Malecka, 2018).

⁶ Scott Sucher, an American cutter specializing in making replicas of historical stones on the basis of computer modelling, informed this author that analysis of a Koh-i-Noor model shows that it must have been wheel cut: “I can’t imagine it being cut being hand-held. The laser scan data also supports this. There is facet rounding, as to be expected by the wheels of the time, but based on my best gem cutting experience (4+ decades), hand holding would have made the rounding far more pronounced.”

⁷ According to Metcalfe’s unpublished report mentioned above, the stone was obtained thousands of years previously from the Koh-i-Noor mine, situated a four-day journey north-west from Masulipatnam, on the banks of the Godavari River (Dalrymple and Anand, 2016). However, this statement could not have been true. The Persian name would not have been used in reference to an ancient Indian mine; moreover, analysis of primary sources does not allow for the assumption that a mine had ever existed under this name.

Figure 3: This illustration of a 'Flat Mughal'-cut diamond appears in various editions of Tavernier's 1692 *Les Six Voyages...*, Vol. 2.

1676; Termezi et al., 1971; Soudavar, 2003). In early Islamic texts, the pearl was the quintessence of lustre, but after the 15th century—most certainly related to popularization in the East of European-cut stones—its place in Muslim literature was taken over by diamonds (Dankoff, 1991; Malecka, in preparation).

The Koh-i-Noor owed its radiance to its facet arrangement, known today as the Mughal cut. This term was introduced in the 1960s for stones of “rather lumpy form with a broad, often asymmetrical base, an upper termination consisting of a set of usually shallow facets or a table, and two or more zones of strip facets parallel to the base and oriented vertically” (Tillander, 1995, p. 64; see also Waite, 1968). The Mughal cut occurred in two versions. As a rule, it was rather flat, with the table usually surrounded by a number of smaller facets. The other version was topped with several facets and usually covered by a large number of small facets. The present author refers to the first of these as ‘Flat Mughals’ (Figure 3) and the second as ‘High Mughals’; the Koh-i-Noor is assigned to the latter (Figure 2).

Cutting History of the Koh-i-Noor

The original artisans who worked the Koh-i-Noor into the Mughal cut, as well as the place where the stone was cut and polished, are not known. In India, diamonds were worked by locals, as well as by European, Jewish and Armenian cutters, who were employed to fashion diamonds in the European way. During the 16th century, such European-cut stones reached prices several hundred percent higher on the Indian subcontinent than in the West, even compared to larger Mughal-cut diamonds

(Malecka, in preparation). Given this, it seems likely that the expert who fashioned the Koh-i-Noor came from India.⁸ According to a contemporary researcher whose analysis of a replica of the stone revealed that its facet corners met precisely at a point (Ogden, 2013), the Koh-i-Noor was polished with the greatest precision, so this specialist must have been a highly skilled professional. He also might have used a Western-type wheel in his work (Ogden, 2013).⁹ As a rule, the most outstanding experts were employed for the royals. Assuming the Koh-i-Noor was the same as the diamond purchased by Akbar in Vijayanagara, it may have been fashioned in the 16th century in the large diamond centre of Vijayanagara by cutters and polishers working for the local ruler.

Mughal-cut diamonds were popular in India because this cut allowed for removal of small flaws, while retaining the greatest possible amount of material and simultaneously giving the diamond the desired brilliance (Haidar and Sardar, 2015). Due to high demand, on the Indian subcontinent such stones were the most expensive among the traditional cuts (Malecka, in preparation). However, this author has not found any evidence that diamonds of this cut were popular in the Near East where, as a rule, Western-cut stones were preferred (Malecka, in preparation; see also Bilirgen and Murat 2001). In the West, diamonds cut in this way were not considered worthy of attention until the second half of the 20th century. As a result, such diamonds were often either subjected to re-cutting upon their arrival in Europe or returned to India for sale (Burton, 1869; Hoey, 1880; Tillander, 1995).

⁸ The widespread declaration that it was the Venetian Hortensio Borgio who worked the Mughal-cut diamond known as the Great Mughal is not true (Malecka, 2016).

⁹ Even though precious stones were worked in India on wheels at the latest in the 13th–14th centuries, such equipment was not used that early for diamonds, for which polishing by hand was preferred (Malecka, in preparation). It is logical to assume that on the Indian subcontinent wheels were first applied to diamonds under Western influence, most certainly in the 16th century (see below). In contrast to Europe, where artisans used iron discs that did not need removal from the base, workers in 17th-century India used steel wheels that had to be taken off daily to be rubbed with emery. The result of these repeated relocations was the uneven run of the polishing tools, which made it impossible to produce diamonds with the high quality characteristic of Westerners' work (Tavernier, 1692). Such steel equipment was still in use by the Indians in the 19th century, although some used iron discs by that time (Newbold, 1843; Hoey, 1880).

Figure 4: According to Tennant (1854a, p. 136), “The flaws in the Koh-i-noor are...F...a large cleavage plane, produced by a fracture...(that) had not been polished...A...a flaw...most skilfully ground nearly out before any of the facets were cut. This flaw seems to proceed from a fracture B...C and E were little notches cut...for the purpose of holding the diamond in its original setting...N, a small flaw...almost required a glass to see it...D, a fracture from a blow or fall, showing at its base a cleavage plane.” Image from Tennant (1854a).

The Koh-i-Noor was received with just such disappointment in Great Britain (Hamlin, 1884). Although Hatleberg (2006) inferred that the Mughal-cut stone was actually a “very brilliant and highly dispersive” diamond, both the British royals and the public who viewed the Mountain of Light at the Great Exhibition of 1851 deemed it not radiant enough (Kinsey, 2009; Roberts, 2012), as they were accustomed to the appearance of brilliant-cut diamonds. In London, the Mughal way of working the diamond was described as so ‘unskillfully executed that its appearance scarcely surpassed that of cut crystal’; other undesirable elements included its irregular egg form, ‘grooves in the sides’, and ‘a small split near the top’ (Figure 4; Anonymous, 1856, p. 221).¹⁰

To eliminate these flaws and make the diamond attractive to the Western public, the stone was refaceted into a brilliant cut. This enhanced its brilliance, as reflected in its name ‘Noor’, but paradoxically it also lost its ‘mountainous’ shape (and 43% of its weight), thus making the name ‘Koh’ inappropriate (Hatleberg, 2006).

Indians’ Views on Cutting Diamonds and Creation of the Mughal Cut

In literature on the subject, there is no conclusive answer to the question of whether the Mughal cut, as well as diamond cutting in general, were initiated in India independently or under Western

influence (King, 1870; Tillander, 1995; Bari, 2001; Klein, 2005). Diamonds were worked on the subcontinent before the Europeans began to cut them towards the end of the 14th century (Tillander, 1995). However, this author could find no texts to support the assertion that these early Indian operations involved processes other than polishing, even though pre-Mughal sources report that hard stones were worked on the subcontinent with the use of various types of specialized tools (Malecka, in preparation). Since the value of diamonds depended on their weight, gem cutters of the Indian subcontinent were probably reluctant to radically diminish them (Malecka, in preparation).

The motivation for cutting diamonds in India was related to concerns about potentially breaking or damaging them. According to Hindu beliefs, gems that were broken, chipped, or had cavities and cracks, as well as those that were flawed or had a particularly coarse surface, were detrimental to the owner, and the amount paid for such stones was of course significantly lower than for good-quality specimens. Thus, the flaws were removed by polishing. Occasionally, this would make the edges of the diamonds less sharp or more even (Garbe, 1882; Varāhamihira and Ramakrishna Bhat, 1982; Shastri and Bhatt, 2008; Tiruttakkatevar and Ryan, 2012). However, at least until the 16th century, it seems that even diamonds without flaws but showing evidence of being worked (i.e. indications of their previous imperfections) brought a lower price in In-

¹⁰ Scott Sucher, who analysed a plaster-cast model of the Koh-i-Noor, informed this author that the ‘split near the top’ could be one of several gashes 2–3 mm deep (three of which, in his view, were man-made) that were present on the stone (Figure 4). According to a British gem expert who examined the Koh-i-Noor in the middle of the 19th century, two of these cavities helped keep the stone in its setting (i.e. C and E in Figure 4; Tennant, 1854a; Malecka, 2018). Although they most certainly were used in this way, in the present author’s view it is doubtful that in India an unblemished specimen would be purposefully defaced by engraving such cavities in it. (See below for the Indians’ views on working diamonds.) According to traditional Indian criteria, such cavities would be counted among diamond flaws described as *gara* or holes on the surface, which could arise during the mining process or from removing inclusions that affected the price of a specimen to a greater degree than would the cavities (Tagore, 1879; Malecka, in preparation). Two of the Koh-i-Noor’s cavities could have resulted from removing flaws, with both being worked in a similar orientation to provide the added benefit of being used to help keep the stone in its setting (Malecka, 2018; see also Brewster, 1863).

Figure 5: A faceting style reminiscent of the Mughal cut is displayed by the garnet in this 6th-century Byzantine ring. Photo © Les Enluminures.

Figure 6: This Mamluk ring from the 13th–14th centuries is mounted with a sapphire cut in a style similar to the Mughal cut. Reproduced with permission from Content (1987); © Derek Content.

dia, and perhaps also in the Near East, than the unblemished, untouched-by-tradesmen rough termed ‘virgins’ (Linschoten et al., 1885; Shammā’ and Tawfīq, 1999; Shcherbina, 2014).

Assuming the Koh-i-Noor was purchased in Vijayanagara by the Great Mughal, it is reasonable to conclude that diamonds were worked in the Mughal cut in India at the latest by the end of the 16th century. So if this cut had appeared on the Indian subcontinent at this time, what were the sources of its inspiration, and where was it most likely created?

In the Near East, cutting of minerals was deemed an Occidental art, at the latest in the 12th century. In a treatise on gems, and as part of a discussion of mounting diamonds in jewellery, an Iranian author of the time mentioned that cutting and polishing were practised in Europe, although exclusively on rubies and emeralds (Nīshābūrī, 2004). A gem expert active around the first quarter of the 16th century in Mughal India denounced the cutting of diamonds as an art of the “Franks” that “did not bring good results”; however, he also admitted that no one was more proficient in this trade than those “immoral infidels” (Rustamdari, 1852 [AH 1268]). A similar view also was held by an Arab gemmologist active at the turn of the 15th/16th centuries, as well as by a Persian-language author from the 15th century who nevertheless maintained that “within the last quarter of the century” it was the Europeans who had best mastered this art (Binesh, 1964; Shammā’ and Tawfīq, 1999).

Such remarks suggest that, in the East in the 15th century, there were known ‘Frankish’ types

of cuts. The table cut and the flat-bottomed Gothic rose cut were widespread in the West at that time, so it is logical to assume that remarks by the Eastern authors pertained to these cuts (Tillander, 1995). In the present author’s view, it also is doubtful that diamonds cut by Westerners would be admired by Indian specialists if Mughal cuts were in use on the subcontinent before this time.

It should be noted that faceting styles reminiscent of the Mughal cut had been done on gems other than diamonds since ancient times. Examples of such stones include an early Byzantine garnet and several sapphires covered with numerous small facets, cavities or ‘dimples’ from about the 10th–14th centuries in India, Vietnam and Egypt (Content, 1987, 2016; Spier, 2012; see Figures 5 and 6). Similarly, as for the Mughal cuts, cavities covering most or all of their exposed surfaces were situated not merely to remove impurities, but also to show the gems to maximum advantage (Content, 2016). However, the present author has not found proof that this type of work—in the case of coloured stones, still appearing in India at least in the 17th century—constituted a direct inspiration for the creation of the Mughal cut for diamonds (Shcherbina, 2014).

In this author’s view, the European cuts admired on the subcontinent were the direct inspiration for Mughal-cut diamonds. The earliest surviving examples this author has found of Mughal-cut diamonds in jewellery that can be dated come from the beginning of the 17th century, while in the West, diamonds reminiscent of the Flat Mughals were worked as early as the first quarter of the

16th century (Keene and Kaoukji, 2001).¹¹ One such stone decorates the hat ornament in a 1519 portrait of Anna Jagellonica (1503–1547), the wife of Holy Roman Emperor Ferdinand I Habsburg (Belozerskaya, 2005; see also Zimerman, 1887). Even though such diamonds theoretically could have had an impact on the origins of the Mughal cut, there is no evidence that they had reached the subcontinent by the early 1500s. Rather, it seems more likely that inspiration for Mughal-cut diamonds came from table- and rose-cut diamonds (see Tillander, 1995, and Galopim de Carvalho, 2014, for illustrations of these cuts). Such stones, including large exceptional ones, were available on the subcontinent at least by the first half of the 16th century; they were exported from Europe or fashioned locally by valued and usually well-paid Westerners (Castañeda, 1554; Vassallo e Silva, 1989; Malecka, in preparation). Among such experts were, for example, Francisco Pereira and Master Pedro, who were both present in the diamond-trading centre of Vijayanagara circa 1548 (Teles e Cunha, 2001).¹²

Most certainly at this time, Indian specialists already were engaged not only in polishing but also in cutting diamonds in Vijayanagara. A description of a mythical city patterned after the capital of the Vijayanagara Empire, written in about 1550 in the Canarese language, includes many gem traders active in its local bazaar, including diamond experts who had their own stalls, where they were engaged in polishing and cutting diamonds into various shapes and sizes (Dallapiccola, 2003). This text unfortunately does not contain information on whether the polishing and cutting were done by the same persons or, as was the case in the West, by different persons.

Evidence that Indians were engaged in diamond cutting under Western influence is found in a Portuguese treatise composed during about 1560–1580 or perhaps a bit earlier. The anonymous author of this work reported that “recently diamonds in India are worked as in our land” and added, in a tone of regret, that Indians “polish them in their own way” (Vassallo e Silva, 1989, p. 137). It is most probable that these remarks referred to early attempts at preparing the Mughal cut.¹³ Information in the work of a Dutch author present on the subcontinent during 1583–1588 also must have pertained

to Mughal-cut diamonds. He mentioned that diamonds prepared at that time in India were “pointed with three corners, h(e)arts, and such like sorts thereby to hide their fault(s)...made in that sort to hold (their) greatness and w(e)ight” (Linschoten et al., 1885, p. 153).

Even though the Mughal cut was effective for retaining the greatest possible amount of the weight, early efforts to prepare such stones apparently were not especially successful, from the point of view of Indian market requirements. The author of the Portuguese treatise stated that, as a result of the Indians’ actions, a rough stone would sometimes lose about 30% and even (as was often the case for Western cuts) 50% of its weight (Vassallo e Silva, 1989).¹⁴

Westerners considered such stones to be badly worked, having “too much thickness underneath” and undoubtedly requiring re-cutting, as both Portuguese and Dutch writers stated that it was not economical for Europeans to buy them (Lin-

¹¹ In the 17th century, Mughal-cut diamonds were especially favoured among Indian Muslims (Ovington, 1690). However, their popularity on the subcontinent started to decline in the 19th century, and by about 1950 finding buyers for Mughal cuts became difficult (Christie’s, 1997; Malecka, in preparation).

¹² Vijayanagara was at that time one of the most important global centres of diamond trade, where stones from elsewhere in India were brought for sale. Other gems also were traded in this centre (Schurhammer and Voretzsch, 1928). For information on European diamond specialists working in Vijayanagara, see Kömmerling-Fitzler (1968).

¹³ It is rather doubtful, in the present author’s view, that cuts prepared then by the Indians were Western-style roses or tables. As mentioned earlier, the market for these unusually costly and exotic stones was not large on the subcontinent at that time; it was most certainly limited to court circles. The wealthy Indians preferred to import such stones from Europe, send rough to be worked in the West or take advantage of the services of European cutters active in India (Malecka, in preparation).

¹⁴ Perhaps the initial attempts by the Indians at working diamonds were not very successful due not only to a lack of capability and proper equipment, but also to the scarcity of specialists with a distinct knowledge of cutting or polishing on the subcontinent. Islamic texts mention two terms describing gem workers: *bakkak*—now usually rendered as a gem engraver, lapidary, or polisher—and *tarash*, or cutter. In the present author’s view, both terms could have been used interchangeably in historical texts as general descriptions of gem workers. The specialists themselves possibly used *bakkak* specifically for a polisher and *tarash* for a cutter, although the meaning of either term may differ depending on the region (Çelebi, 1896; Kāshānī and Afshār, 1966/1967 [AH 1345]).

schoten et al., 1885, p. 153; Vassallo e Silva, 1989). The Portuguese writer maintained that it was more beneficial to buy ‘developed and cleaned’ diamonds from ‘Moors’ (most probably Muslims active in India), whose stones could be recut without losing much of their weight. Such diamonds probably were already polished in the mining areas according to the Indian custom of removing flaws (Vassallo e Silva, 1989, pp. 136–137; Malecka, in preparation).

What factors contributed to the rise of the Mughal cut? It is known that in India, hundreds of years before Europeans arrived there, diamonds with smooth polished edges were popular and considered auspicious (Hultzsch et al., 1916; Malecka, in preparation). As a result of these polishing activities, specimens with big tables probably existed already, although surviving examples of such stones are impossible to date earlier than Mughal times (Ivanov et al., 1984; Keene and Kaoukji, 2001; Tān, 2002). Although pre-Mughal Indian diamond experts were probably familiar with diamonds with tables, we have no evidence to support the placement of triangular facets in a regular pattern around the tables prior to Western influence. On some Mughal-cut diamonds, the first row of facets around the table was composed of trapezoids or rectangles, possibly inspired by Western table cuts. In the case of the High Mughals, the table was replaced by a small number of facets, which brings to mind early rose cuts (Tillander, 1995). Of course, the final form of the stone was determined by several factors: size and shape of the rough, type and positioning of flaws and directional hardness anisotropy, which in consideration of the primitive tools used at the time, was the greatest challenge for the cutters (Hart, 2015).

The Mughal cut was considered to be a local, Indian version of the rose cut. Prior to the 20th century, Mughal-cut diamonds (now described simply as ‘Indian’ or ‘worked on in India’) were described in Europe as ‘roses’ or ‘Indian roses’ (Ujfalvy-Bourdon, 1885; Nasiri, 1945 [AH 1364]; Copeland, 1960; Rybakov, 1975; see also Tarshis, 2000). It should be mentioned that the Mughal cut had ‘flowery’ connotations on the subcontinent. In conversations with this author, Indian gem merchants described High Mughals with the term *kanwal*, which in the Hindustani language

means ‘water lily’.¹⁵ In reference to Flat Mughals, the present author’s interlocutors used the term *parab* (‘flat diamond’ in Hindustani; see also Bala Krishnan and Ramamrutham, 2001). In the literature, the stones described today as Mughal cuts appear under the names *villandi* or *bullandi* (Persian ‘buland’ or ‘high’), as well as *polki*, which is also used on the subcontinent to refer to rose cuts (Untracht, 1997; Shcherbina, 2014; Shor, 2016). It is possible that the same terms were used in somewhat different ways for the various methods of working in different areas of the Indian subcontinent at varying times.

Determining where in India the Mughal cut could have originated is not an easy task. It most likely happened in one of the centres in which European gem experts stayed: the above-mentioned Vijayanagara; Calicut, in which gem experts from the West already were present at the end of the 15th century; Cochin, the main seat of Portuguese India in 1503–1530; or Goa, which was conquered by the Portuguese in 1510. Through this last city, Western goldsmithing techniques reached the subcontinent, imported by Europeans as well as by Indians who travelled to Lisbon as early as the first quarter of the 16th century (Alves, 1935; Matos, 1989; see also Pissurlencar, 1936). Western diamond cuts appeared in Goa as imports, and also through the actions of the European workers operating in this city, among whom the Flemish and Portuguese distinguished themselves (Linschoten et al., 1885; see also Vassallo e Silva, 1995, 2004). Given this, it is logical to assume that around the middle of the 16th century diamonds were worked in Goa. In the present author’s view, it is most likely that Goa is where the Mughal cut was created, as an example of Indo-Western syncretism typical of the artistic creativity in that city.

It is tempting to suggest that the Indian community of diamond workers were instrumental to

¹⁵ It is interesting that the term ‘water lily diamonds’ might have been used in other parts of the Islamic world to describe rose cuts. It is known, for example, that stones fashioned in the shape of a water lily were ordered in the 1660s from the Dutch by a certain Sumatran royal (Chijs, 1893). In the Malay world at that time, the rose cut was considered exotic and was ordered from Western cutters, so it is highly probable that those ‘water lily diamonds’ were the same as roses. Diamonds described as *niliiferi* or water lily also were mentioned in an Ottoman text (Malecka, in preparation).

the rise of the Mughal cut, and in the present author's view the most probable candidates are the Gujaratis who were present in Portuguese Goa in the 16th century. It is known that the Gujaratis, who had already played an important role in the diamond trade for many centuries, had been moving between Goa and the diamondiferous Deccan area during the Mughal era (Orta, 1891; Malecka, in preparation). In view of the Gujaratis' presence in this centre in which Europeans were active, it is possible that the experts belonging to this community created the Mughal cut, modelling on the work of their Western colleagues but bearing in mind the aesthetic and material needs of the Indians. The above-mentioned pentagonal facets, which resemble rectangles with triangular pinnacles, and gave the stone a flower-like appearance, evoke a motif known from 16th-century Gujarati decorative art: a central medallion surrounded by rectangular, sharply finished 'petals' (Vassallo e Silva, 2001).

Conclusion

Various versions of a story regarding Nadir Shah's acquisition of the Koh-i-Noor diamond and his naming of this stone gradually became established during the 19th century, in India as well as probably in Great Britain. The name *Koh-i-Noor*, in keeping with Eastern tradition, was directly related to the appearance of the stone (i.e. its radiance and shape), as displayed by its Mughal cutting style. Assuming the Koh-i-Noor to be Emperor Akbar's stone, it is logical to conclude that cutting and polishing of this diamond took place in the 16th century by an Indian specialist. It also is possible that the diamond was worked in the kingdom of Vijayanagara, where it might have originated.

In the present author's view, Mughal-cut diamonds appeared on the Indian subcontinent under the influence of European table and rose cuts. The Mughal cut was created most certainly before 1550, possibly in Goa through the Gujaratis. The largest market for diamonds worked in this way, at least prior to 1565, was probably Vijayanagara. This cutting style facilitated the removal of flaws that disfigured a diamond or made it susceptible to breakage, while simultaneously maintaining the greatest volume of material.

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Acknowledgements

The author thanks Al Gilbertson (Gemological Institute of America, Carlsbad, California, USA), Scott Sucher (The Stonecutter, Tijeras, New Mexico, USA), Dr Sandra Hindman (Les Enluminures, Paris, France), Dr Beatriz Chadour-Sampson (Society of Jewellery Historians, London), Derek Content (London) and three anonymous reviewers for their assistance with preparing this article.